

PROCESSING OF POROUS POLYMER COMPOSITES FOR APPLICATION TO BONE TISSUE ENGINEERING

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SUMMARY: Bone is a natural porous composite structure, consisting of an organic matrix of collagen fibres and a mineral support of hydroxyapatite. It has unique properties of remodelling, adapting to external mechanical stress, preserving high mechanical performance, and self-healing in the case of small defects. Larger bone defects can be repaired using, allografts, autografts, and more recently, artificial grafts. This study focused on composite scaffolds based on polymer matrices and prepared by a solvent-free method. First three different techniques to mix ceramic and polymer are optimised and compared. Melt-extrusion is finally selected to prepare composite preforms, further foamed with supercritical CO₂. The presence of fillers resulted in less expanded cellular structures, but still with interconnected pores, of suitable diameters, for bone tissue engineering applications. Fillers also improved foam mechanical resistance. Finally developed composite foams were shown to be biocompatible with bone cells.

KEYWORDS: bioresorbable polymer, calcium phosphates, supercritical foaming, bone tissue engineering.

INTRODUCTION

Bone is a natural cellular composite, with a gradient structure going from a loose interconnected core to an outer dense wall, thus minimising bone weight while maintaining a high mechanical performance [1]. Bone can be repaired using either auto- or allo- grafts, which, however, have a limited availability, or present pathogen transmission risks, respectively. Synthetic tissue grafts are therefore investigated in order to provide porous scaffolds, seeded with the appropriate type of cells, as templates for tissue regeneration [2]. This study focused on composite scaffolds based on polymer matrices. Several methods, usually involving the use of organic solvents, were reported to prepare such structures: fibre mesh [3, 4], solvent casting / particulate leaching [5, 6], emulsion freeze-drying or thermally induced phase separation [7-9], 3D printing [10]... Supercritical CO₂ foaming was chosen as a flexible and solvent-free technique to manufacture cellular structures [11], with the possibility of adding fibres or functional fillers [12]. The objectives were to propose and

optimize solvent-free process in order to prepare bioresorbable composite scaffolds suitable for bone tissue engineering applications, and to investigate the effect of fillers on the structural and mechanical properties of foams. Before foaming composites, a homogeneous mixing of the two components was required [13]. Three mixing techniques will therefore be investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

A bioresorbable poly(L-lactic acid) (PLA, I.V.=1.6 dL/g, $T_m=182$ °C) (Boehringer Ingelheim, Germany), and two ceramic powders, hydroxyapatite (HA, nanometric size, 50 m²/g), and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP, micrometric size, 1-2 m²/g) (Dr R. Mathys Foundation, Switzerland), were used as received, after drying overnight at 105 °C and under vacuum, in order to avoid polymer hydrolysis [14]. Calcium phosphates were added to PLA in order to improve mechanical resistance, to regulate pH during construct degradation, and to favor mineralization, owing to their intrinsic osteoconductive properties.

Composite preforms

For composite foaming, a preliminary homogeneous mixing of ceramic powder and polymer pellets was needed. Three techniques were tested, optimised in order to obtain a homogeneous filler dispersion, and compared.

Mixing in the dry state

PLA pellets were first grinded in liquid nitrogen with a small mixer. They were then mixed with dried fillers in glass vials to prevent electrostatic adhesion on bottle walls. Mixing was carried out in a 3D mixer (Turbola T2C) at 42 rpm. Four mixing times were tested: 5, 15, 30 and 60 min. Compression molding was finally achieved under vacuum to prevent polymer degradation, in a 20 mm diameter mould (Fontjine Holland Table Press, The Netherlands). The effects of temperature and pressure, varied from 185 to 205 °C, and 10 to 32 MPa respectively, were investigated, with a sintering time of 30 min.

Solvent-based method

PLA pellets were first dissolved in chloroform (Aldrich) to prepare a 10 % (wt/vol) polymer solution, stirred 2 h at 60 °C. Ceramic powder was then slowly added to the solution. After 30 min stirring a homogeneous suspension was obtained. Solvent was evaporated overnight at ambient atmosphere, and further under vacuum during 48 h.

Melt-extrusion

PLA pellets and ceramic particles were mixed in the dry state prior to extrusion. A micro-compounder (Micro 5 Compounder; DSM, The Netherlands) with two conical co-rotating screws, of small capacity (5 cm³), was used to prepare ceramic/polymer blends, under a flow of nitrogen to limit polymer degradation. Set temperatures (200 and 205 °C), screw rotation speeds (100, 150 and 200 rpm) and residence times (1 to 4 min) were varied in order to determine the optimum mixing condition.

Scaffold preparation

The foaming equipment was composed of a custom made high pressure chamber (Autoclave France, France) and a computerized acquisition data system. Samples, PLA pellets or composite preforms with homogeneously dispersed HA or β -TCP, were loaded in cylindrical open moulds, placed in the pressure vessel. Supercritical CO₂ (pure>99.995%, SL Gas, Switzerland) was used as it was shown to better dissolve in poly (α -hydroxy acids) than N₂ or He [15], because of specific interactions between CO₂ and carboxyl groups [16]. Pressure and temperature were increased up to saturation pressure P_{sat} (100-250 bar) and 195 °C respectively. Polymer saturation by supercritical CO₂ was completed after 10 min. Foam

expansion was then achieved by sudden gas release, which induced the creation of gas nuclei due to supersaturation. These nuclei grew to form the cellular structure. Simultaneously to pressure reduction, temperature decreased; this resulted in an increase of polymer viscosity and progressively fixed foam architecture. Solidification and re-crystallisation of the polymer definitively froze the porous structure. An initial depressurization rate dP/dt (2-15 bar/s), controlled by a back-pressure regulator, and a maximum cooling rate dT/dt (3-7 °C/s) were significant parameters which affected pore expansion and stabilization.

Foam analysis

Samples were cut with a razor blade and gold-coated to avoid charge accumulation and prevent sample damage. Using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM, Philips XL30, Holland), specimens were observed under a high tension of 3 kV with secondary electrons for simple topographic observation. To detect particle distribution (chemical contrast), back-scattered electrons were used on polished surfaces, with a higher tension of 7 kV. A 3D structure was also characterised by micro-computed tomography (μ CT, Scanco Medical, Switzerland) of small cylinders (height and diameter 8 mm). Measurements were performed with an X-ray beam with energy of 50 kVp, and a spatial resolution of 12 μ m. 3D reconstructions and foam structural parameters, such as porosity, pore diameter, degree of anisotropy, were computed. Compression behaviour of foams was evaluated on specimens of measured density. Samples were prepared paying a special attention to obtaining parallel surfaces, perpendicular to the testing direction. Measurements were carried out on a Universal Testing Machine (UTS Test Systeme, Germany), with a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min. Elastic modulus E^* was evaluated from the initial linear elastic part of the stress-strain curve, and ultimate strength σ^* from the plateau. For each condition, three to five samples were tested. Data on the graphs represent their average, and error bars the standard deviations.

Biocompatibility

Biocompatibility of neat polymer and composite scaffolds with human foetal bone cells was also checked. Cells were obtained from the Laboratory of Orthopaedic Research bank of bone cells, comprising 4 foetal donors at the end of March 2004. Biopsies were obtained in accordance to the Ethics Committee of the university Hospital in Lausanne (Ethical Protocol 51/01). Scaffolds were sterilised overnight in phosphate-buffered saline, pH 7.4, containing penicillin and streptomycin at concentrations of 100 units/mL and 100 μ g/mL, respectively (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA). Bone cells were cultured in Bulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium DMEM Glutamax (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA), 10% Foetal Calf Serum FCS (Sigma Aldrich, St Louis, MO), at 37 °C, in a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere, and seeded onto scaffolds in a 24-well plate at a density of 20'000 cells/well. To induce differentiation, a culture medium was then implemented with osteogenic factors, being L-ascorbic acid 50 μ g/mL (Sigma Aldrich, St Louis, MO), β -glycerophosphate 1 mM (Sigma Aldrich, St Louis, MO), dexamethasone 10 nM (Sigma Aldrich, St Louis, MO) and vitamin 1 α ,25-(OH)₂D₃ 10 nM (Alexis Biochemicals, San Diego, CA), and refreshed every second day up to four weeks. Gene expression was quantified by real time RT-PCR (Reverse Transcription-Polymerase Chain Reaction), using specific primers for osteoblastic markers such as *cbfa1*, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), α 1 chain of collagen I, and osteocalcin (bone gla protein BGP). Specific primers were designed with the Primer Express Software (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA), and purchased from Integrated DNA Technologies (Coralville, IA). The standard curve method was used for quantification. The expression of the targeted gene was normalised to the housekeeping gene 18S chosen as an endogenous control.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bulk composites were first obtained by three different techniques. Preforms were then foamed, and composites foams were analysed in order to determine the effect of fillers on structural parameters, mechanical properties and biocompatibility.

Composite preforms

Using the dry mixing method, after 1 h of powder mixing, the polymer surface was completely covered by ceramic particles. Sintering was then necessary in order to achieve cohesion between the two components, and to avoid ceramic dispersion in the foaming chamber. Sintering does not induce a large flow of polymer, thus preserving the particle distribution obtained after the first step. Pressure and temperature of sintering were shown to have significant effects [17]. After optimization, sintering was finally conducted with parameters adjusted at 30 min, 195 °C and 20 MPa. A network of ceramic particles surrounded polymer pellets, therefore not resulting in a homogeneous combination of the two components (Fig. 1a). These contacts between ceramic grains could be a drawback in the final foam, where they would provide a preferential path for crack propagation, which decreases mechanical resistance instead of improving it. Moreover, polymer and ceramic rich zones of different viscosities, inducing different foaming behaviors, would be a drawback to obtaining foams of homogeneous morphology. This technique will therefore not be considered further.

In the solvent-based technique, polymer solution concentration had to be adjusted [18]. When the solution was too thin, sedimentation of ceramic particles occurred; on the opposite, when it was too thick, it became difficult to add large amounts of ceramic. Both cases finally led to an uneven distribution of ceramic fillers [19]. When polymer concentration was optimized, a homogeneous dispersion of ceramic in the polymer matrix was obtained (Fig. 1b). However, proton-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (¹H-NMR, Brücker 200 MHz, in d₂-methylene chloride CD₂Cl₂) revealed after evaporation the presence of residual chloroform. This may be detrimental for biocompatibility studies and cell behaviour [20].

Melt-extrusion was the third technique tested. An increase in residence time induced a more homogeneous dispersion of fillers, with a closer contact between components. However, there was also the risk of polymer degradation by hydrolysis, as evaluated by DSC with a slight decrease in T_g and T_m. Higher screw speeds increased the force, and thus pressure, exerted on the melt, therefore decreasing the residual macroporosity and leading to a more homogeneous composite. A higher set temperature led to an improved dispersion of the fillers in the matrix, because of a lower viscosity of the polymer and higher β-TCP (or HA) wetting [21, 22]. A set temperature of 205 °C, a screw speed of 100 rpm during 4 min of mixing were finally selected to obtain dense rods with a homogeneous dispersion of fillers in the polymer (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1: Distribution of β-TCP particles in PLA after a) mixing in the dry state, b) dispersion in a polymer–solvent solution, and c) melt-extrusion. Similar results were obtained with HA.

Solvent and melt-prepared composites, with a good filler distribution, were then tested using tensile tests at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min (UTS Test Systeme, Germany) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Comparison of tensile modulus, experimental and calculated, of bulk composites HA (β -TCP) / PLA after solvent and melt processing with initial raw PLA.

In the case of the neat polymer processed by the solvent-based method, a decrease in tensile modulus was observed due to plasticization by chloroform molecules. The addition of fillers to the matrix improved the tensile modulus. Large variations were due to some particle aggregates creating ceramic rich zones, in particular with 10 wt% fillers, where preferential rupture occurred. This can also explain the difference between theoretical calculations and experimental moduli. Kikuchi *et al.* [23] reported heterogeneous compounds of HA and PLA prepared in a chloroform solution, resulting in brittle composites. On the opposite, composites obtained in our study were rather ductile as a consequence of the presence of residual chloroform acting as a plasticizer, provided fillers were well dispersed.

With the melt approach, tensile moduli higher than with the solvent-based method were obtained. Tensile moduli increased with higher ceramic contents, with experimental values close to theoretical ones. The addition of greater amounts of ceramic theoretically increases composite modulus, which is interesting for bulk applications. However, only contents up to 10 wt% were considered here as a compromise to obtain adequate viscosity for the foaming process. In fact a high filler content corresponds to a high viscosity of the melt which limits foam expansion, and therefore the degree of porosity.

Finally with tensile experiments, melt extrusion appeared to give more homogeneous results, with higher moduli than solvent prepared composites. Melt extrusion was therefore used preferentially to combine PLA and ceramics prior to foaming.

Foam analyses: morphology and mechanical analysis

The effects of foaming parameters on foam architecture and properties were already described for microcellular foams [24] and in a previous study for non-filled PLA [25]. As they are similar in the case of filled matrices, this study focused on the effect of fillers on cellular structure and properties.

Fig. 3 compares the morphology of neat and β -TCP filled PLA foams obtained under similar processing conditions. Using ceramics, more heterogeneous and less expanded structures with more closed pores were obtained. In fact a higher filler content limited gas expansion, because of an increased polymer viscosity [26]. A higher pore density could also be observed, as ceramic particles could serve as preferential sites for heterogeneous nucleation. The regularity of foam morphology was highly dependant on filler dispersion in the polymer matrix.

Fig. 3: Comparison of foam morphology without and with ceramics, processed in similar conditions. a) PLA, and b) PLA+2.5wt%β-TCP. Similar results were obtained with HA fillers.

Foam morphology was more heterogeneous with HA than with β-TCP fillers. This may be explained by the fact that HA primary particles, revealed by TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy), tended to form aggregates of various sizes. Consequently polymer- and ceramic- rich zones were present, leading to large pores coexisting with smaller ones. Therefore this confirms that a homogeneous dispersion of ceramic particles in the polymer was required in order to process homogeneous cellular structures. In both cases, ceramic particles were embedded in the polymer, as shown by photos of edge cross-sections (Fig. 4). This ceramic distribution should favour an efficient reinforcement of the foam, provided fillers were homogeneously dispersed, and did not come in contact with each other.

Fig. 4: a) β-TCP and b) HA particles embedded in composite foam walls

A higher filler content resulted in an increased foam density and an increased average pore diameter (Fig. 5). The latter can be explained by a good interface between filler and matrix, which limited gas loss and therefore favoured pore growth [27]. The effect of fillers on pore growth is, however, still discussed. Zhang *et al.* [28] reported a significant influence of particles on cellular structure only if there was a strong interaction between fillers and polymer. Zeng *et al.* [29] observed a decrease in pore size with higher nanoclay content in polystyrene.

Fig. 5: The effect of ceramic content on composite foam density and mean pore diameter. Error bars of standard deviation are not given for graph clarity. Full and dashed lines only indicate trends.

In summary, for a given foaming condition, a higher filler content limited gas expansion, thus increasing foam density. A morphology study of composite foams showed that fillers were mainly located in pore walls and that a homogeneous dispersion of ceramic particles in polymer was required before foaming in order to create a regular cellular structure, controlled only by processing parameters. Selected foaming conditions with an intermediate ceramic content of 5 wt%, which seems to be the maximum allowed, gave rise to partially interconnected pores, with a diameter of around 200-400 μm , which would be suitable characteristics for the targeted application.

To complete analysis, PLA and composite foam samples were tested in compression. Fig. 6 shows a decrease of foam modulus with increasing porosity, as described by the Gibson and Ashby model [1]. With filled foams, modulus up to 250 MPa and ultimate strength up to 6 MPa could be reached. For a given porosity, higher moduli were experimentally measured using reinforced PLA than with neat PLA. Similarly, for a given modulus, a higher porosity can be reached with fillers than without. This evidenced the potential of fillers to improve polymer foam mechanical resistance. Error bars can be explained by the fact that the three to five specimens tested for one condition may be heterogeneous and of different densities although they were all taken from the core of a same batch.

Cubic samples were also tested parallel (longitudinal) and perpendicularly (transversely) to the foaming direction. Longitudinal moduli were measured up to 1.5 times greater than transverse moduli. This anisotropy was induced by the processing technique, giving rise to elongated and preferentially oriented pores, described by μCT measurements, which evaluated a degree of anisotropy of between 1.1 and 1.7 [30]. Bone has a similar transverse isotropic behaviour, presenting a higher mechanical resistance longitudinally than transversally.

Fig. 6: Compressive behavior. Comparison between neat PLA, and PLA filled with 5 wt % HA or β -TCP.

Compressive measurements therefore evidenced the reinforcement effect of ceramic fillers on PLA foams, and indicated that prepared porous structures had an anisotropic behaviour. Morphology and mechanical properties are thus promising for bone tissue engineering applications, provided prepared structures are biocompatible.

Biocompatibility

Composite foams were tested in order to evaluate their ability to allow cell growth, proliferation and differentiation. Human foetal bone cells were chosen for their higher proliferation capacity and present less immunological compatibility issues, and therefore a therapeutic potential [31]. A comparison with human adult bone cells was also carried out and

indicated that foetal bone cells proliferated more rapidly than adult bone cells, in contact of scaffolds [32].

Fig. 7a indicates that cells colonised well the surface of the scaffolds. Partial or total occlusion of pores was observed, with cell layers lying down across pore volume. Cells were also shown to penetrate inside the porous structure.

Cell colonisation and the expression of their osteoblastic phenotype were evaluated by real time RT-PCR. The expression of ribosomal 18S gene showed that cells did proliferate on all scaffolds. The expression of genes, such as core binding factor *cbfa1*, a critical factor for osteoblasts differentiation and function [33], alkaline phosphatase (ALP), a cell membrane associated enzyme [34], α 1 chain of collagen I, which composes 85-90% of the total organic bone matrix, and osteocalcin (bone gla protein BGP), one of the most abundant non-collagenous protein in bone [33], confirmed that cells were able to differentiate in the osteoblast lineage. This differentiation was more pronounced on composite foams than on pure polymer structures, due to the presence of osteoconductive ceramic fillers (Fig. 7b). When completely differentiated, cells induce the mineralization of extra-cellular matrix. Mineral crystals were in fact observed on scaffold surfaces. Chemical analyses by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy under SEM and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) detected Ca and P elements, therefore confirming the presence of calcium phosphates on the PLA surface after foetal bone cell proliferation and differentiation.

Fig. 7: Human foetal bone cells proliferate and differentiate on composite constructs. a) Cells spread on matrix surface, and b) *cbfa1*, ALP, α chain 1 collagen I, and osteocalcin, evaluated by RT-PCR, revealed expression of osteoblastic phenotype, after four weeks of exposition to osteogenic factors.

CONCLUSIONS

A solvent-free process was developed to prepare composite cellular structures with morphology and mechanical properties suitable for bone tissue engineering applications. Three techniques were investigated in order to homogeneously disperse fillers in the matrix. First, compression moulding of a ceramic – polymer powder mixture led to a composite with ceramic and polymer rich zones. Second, solvent dispersion and melt-extrusion resulted in a good filler distribution, with, however, better mechanical properties when using the latter method. Before supercritical CO₂ foaming, composites were therefore prepared by melt-extrusion. Fillers were then shown to limit pore expansion, although using suitable foaming parameters allowed obtaining structures with interconnected pores, of diameter between 200-400 μm, and with homogeneously dispersed particles in pore walls. The presence of fillers also improved foam mechanical resistance, while maintaining anisotropic properties. Finally, developed porous composites were shown to be biocompatible with human foetal bone cells, which proliferated, differentiated and induced mineralization of extra-cellular matrix.

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